

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation and Evolution of Polyherbal Shampoo

Vaishali Bhavale*, Aarti Dangode, Priya Jaware, Dr. Santosh Payghan

Rajesh Bhaiyya Tope College of B. Pharmacy, CHH. Sambhajinagar.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 16 April. 2025

Keywords:

Herbal Shampoo,
Nourishing Property, Beal
Fruit, Curry Leaves,
Aloevera, Lemon Juice,
Flexseed, Reetha.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15229505

ABSTRACT

Creating and testing a herbal shampoo using curry leaves and beal fruit, two herbal plants, was the aim of the current study. These plants are used in the production of herbal shampoo. One of the cosmetics used on a daily basis is shampoo. Synthetic detergents and preservatives have occasionally had a negative impact on consumers. The formulated shampoo incorporates beal fruits, which are utilized to diminish hair loss and combat dandruff, while curry leaves are recognized for their advantageous properties in hair care. The treatment of hair and scalp primarily involves the application of shampoo for effective yet gentle cleansing. However, for years, shampoo has been regarded not merely as a cosmetic product with purifying functions, but also as essential for maintaining the health and beauty of hair, imparting luster and enhancing manageability. The most common problem in people is related to the dry Shampoo is the most basic cosmetic used for hair, containing antimicrobial agent and other ingredient commonly used. The main function of shampoo is to clean the hair properly and reduce the dandruff. In present work we have formulated onion and eucalyptus oil herbal shampoo for the dry hair. The dryness is the most prevalent issue among people. Research on dry hair remedies was therefore conducted. The formula was assessed for a number of factors. This herbal shampoo's benefits include greater nutrition and nourishment for hair follicles, accelerated hair development, and relief from dryness. Research on dry hair remedies was therefore conducted. To make sure the shampoo was safe and effective, it was put through evaluation criteria.

INTRODUCTION

The essential component of human beauty is hair. Since ancient times, people have used herbs to clean, adorn, and manage their hair. These factors

drew the public to herbal products because they are less costly and have less adverse effects. In addition to its capacity to clean hair, it also gives hair a glossy finish and keeps it manageable and oil-free.

***Corresponding Author:** Vaishali Bhavale

Address: Rajesh Bhaiyya Tope College of B. Pharmacy, CHH. Sambhajinagar.

Email ✉: bhavlevishali@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig 1.0 Hair Folicale

➤ **Herbal Shampoo:**

Shampoo is a liquid or cream form of soap or detergent used to cleanse hair. Shampoo is a hair care product used to clean hair that usually comes in a viscous liquid form. Shampoo is intended to eliminate undesired accumulation between hairs without removing so much sebum that it becomes unmanageable. The most popular method of treating hair is shampooing. The main purpose of shampoos is to cleanse the scalp and hair. Even though herbal shampoos are safer and perform better than synthetic ones, it seems unlikely that they would be widely used by customers in the current market.

Ideal Properties of shampoo:

1. To make the hair smooth and shiny.
2. Produce good amount of foam.
3. Should not cause irritant to scalp, skin and eye.
4. Should completely, effectively remove dirt.
5. Impart pleasant fragrance to hair.

Functions of Shampoo:

1. It should effectively and completely remove dirt or soil.
2. It should effectively wash the hair.
3. It should produce a good amount of foam to satisfy the user.
4. It should be readily removed by rinsing with water.
5. It should impart a pleasant fragrance to the hair.
6. It should not have any side effects or causes irritation to the skin and eye.

Classification of Shampoo:

1. Based on Appearance

- Liquid shampoo or lotion shampoo
- Gel shampoo or Solid shampoo
- Cream shampoo
- Oil shampoo

Based on Use or Function:

- Conditioning shampoo
- Antidandruff shampoo
- Therapeutic shampoo
- Baby shampoo

- Clarifying shampoo

3. Based on origin:

- Herbal shampoo
- Egg shampoo

• **Hair Hygiene:**

• **Frequent washing:** To get rid of product buildup, perspiration, oil, and grime, you must wash your hair on a regular basis. Your hair type and personal preferences will determine how often you should wash your hair. For most people, washing their hair two to three times a week is adequate.

• **Scalp care:** Because your scalp is so important to hair cleanliness, take note of its condition. While shampooing, gently massage your scalp to encourage blood flow and create a favorable environment for hair growth. Steer clear of styling products and high heat that could dry out or irritate your scalp.

• **Proper Drying:** Use a soft towel to gently pat dry your hair after washing it. Steer clear of excessive rubbing as this can harm your hair strands by creating friction. When at all feasible, let your hair air dry because blow dryers' high heat can cause breakage and dryness. Before utilizing any heat styling equipment, mist them with a heat protectant spray.

• **Brushing and detangling:** Frequent brushing keeps your hair healthy and shiny by distributing natural oils from the scalp to the individual hair strands. To gently untangle your hair, begin at the ends and work your way up with a soft-bristled brush or a wide-toothed comb. Avoid pushing or tugging too much since this can lead to breaking.

• **Protection from Environmental Factors:** Keep your hair safe from damaging elements like intense sunlight, high winds, and chlorinated water. To shield your hair from UV radiation and other environmental contaminants, put on a cap or

wrap it in a scarf. Rinse your hair well to get rid of any residue after swimming in saltwater or chlorinated pools, then use a hydrating conditioner.

• **Healthy Lifestyle:** The condition of your hair is influenced by your general health and wellbeing. In order to promote healthy hair development, keep up a balanced diet full of proteins, vitamins, and minerals. Maintain proper hydration, control your stress levels, and get adequate sleep because these things can also impact the state of your hair.

2. Review Of Literature:

1. Vishal Kulkarni, Pingale Prashant, Et Al Shikakai and reetha have anti-dandruff properties; the current study examines the impact of snakegourd, shika kai, and reetha on this property. This study demonstrates the effectiveness of each herb's anti-dandruff properties as well as how those properties alter when combined in varying concentrations. These studies come to the conclusion that, when creating a decent anti-dandruff shampoo, are individual herbs sufficient or do they need to be combined for optimal results? To gain a better understanding of the effects of herbs' anti-dandruff properties, the current study also compares the prepared and marketet preparations.

2. Padmini K., Srikanth J., Lohita M., Swetha K., Rao P. Vengal, and Preethi P. Jaya (2013) The most popular hair treatment is shampooing. The main purpose of shampoos is to cleanse the hair and scalp. A more drastic strategy for making herbal shampoo more widely used would be to alter customer expectations by emphasizing efficacy and safety. The focus of this research is on composition, types, evaluation techniques, and a brief overview of herbal shampoo formulations.

3. Suraj Maurya, Manoj Kumar Yadav, Piyush Yadav, Pawan Maurya, Satyam Jaysawal, and

Shashikant Maurya. (2021) Natural hair care products like herbal shampoo are used to get rid of oil, grime, and dandruff while also strengthening, darkening, and encouraging hair growth. Additionally, it gives the hair gloss, softness, and smoothness.

4. Deo S, Itankar P, and Utane R. (2017) We are losing the beauty, quality, strength, volume, and gloss of our hair by using commercial products. Every commercial product, including cleaners, has a harmful ingredient that causes hair damage.

5. Kundan J. Tiwari and Vinayak M. Chavan Aditya S. Bhor and Kiran A. Suryavanshi (2019) A number of factors, including pH, foam formation, viscosity, conditioning, and wet ability, were assessed during the laboratory-scale formulation in order to guarantee its efficacy and safety.

3.Rational Of the Study: - Need of Work:

□ Herbal Shampoo Has Become More Advantageous Than Chemical Shampoo:

- Herbal shampoos are non-irritant and they have anti-dandruff properties.
- They are less harmful and have very few or no side effects.
- They are less harmful and have very few or no side effects.
- Herbal shampoo are the better option for even the most sensitive skin.
- It doesn't contain any abrasive additives.

Herbs and their extracts have been used for hair management, cleaning, and beauty since ancient times. These days, cosmetic products made with natural substances are beginning to be utilized again, following a real trend. It's interesting to note that many plants have positive effects on hair and are frequently utilized in shampoos due to their

high vitamin, amino acid, sugar, glycoside, phytohormone, bioflavonoid, fruit acid, and essential oil content. As a result, numerous research studies on shampoos made with natural elements have been created. These products must be effective and safe for prolonged use, guaranteeing mild detergency and a pleasing appearance. However, choosing these natural chemicals and developing innovative formulation procedures are the key challenges in the tough task of creating cosmetics utilizing natural raw materials. Commercially available herbal shampoos, both liquid and powder, are still based on synthetic functional components that are enhanced with natural raw materials or extracts, according to Bellare et al. According to a number of Indian literature research, herbal shampoos are typically made with common traditional medications that Indians typically use to wash their hair.

Aim:-

Cleaning the hair and scalp, regulating oil production, nourishing, enhancing hair texture, preserving hair color, encouraging shine, resolving scalp problems, and guaranteeing safe use of natural components are all goals of herbal shampoo formulations.

Objectives:-

1. The Objective Of This Study Is To Formulate The Herbal Shampoo For Natural Hair Growth and Less Side Effects.
2. To Study The Herbal Shampoos For Hair Growth Are Made To Strengthen The Hair Follicles by Giving Essential Oils And Nourishment All Through The Root And Follicles.

3. This, In Tum, Promotes Hair Growth And Stimulates The Formation Of New And Healthy Hair Roots.

4. Regular Usage Of Herbal Shampoos Can Do Wonders For Your Hairs.

5. Herbal Shampoo Provides Natural Colours To The Hairs

6. Herbal Shampoo Comes With Natural Herbal Extracts With Less Chemicals Which Leads To less Side Effects.

7. To Eliminate Harm ful synthetic ingredients from shampoo formulation and substituent them with a safe natural ingredients.

4. Plan Of Work: -

• Selection of pure drug

1. Beal fruit
2. Curry leaves
3. Flexseeds
4. Reetha
5. Aleo vera
6. Lemon juice
7. Hibiscus Flowers

• Preparation of material and methods:

1. Preparation of Distilled Water:

Distilled water was prepared in laboratory by using soxhlet apparatus. Tape water was taken in round bottom flask . later it was put on the soxhlet extraction . After 30 min.- 1 hr. distilled water was collected from process

• Experimental design-

Formulation and evolution of herbal shampoo

- Result & discussion
- Conclusion
- Reference

5. Selection of Pure Drug

1. Beal Fruit:

Synonym: golden apple, Japanese bitter orange, stone apple, wood apple.

Botanical Name: Aegle marmelos L.

Biological Sorce: The biological source of beal fruit is Aegle marmelos

Family: Rutaceae

Fig. 5.1 Beal Fruit

Chemical Constitute:

- Vitamins: Certain vitamins, such as biotin (vitamin B7), are typically added in hair care products. Biotin is believed to increase hair development and improve hair health.
- Antioxidant & anti-inflammatory flavonoids and phenols Kaempferol, rutin, and quercetin aid in shielding hair from environmental harm and oxidative stress.

Uses:

- Improve scalp health
- Nourishment of scalp

- Promotes hair growth over

2. Curry Leaves:

Synonyms: sweet neem leaves

Botanical Name: *Murraya Koenigii*

Biological Source: It is common name curry leaves trees is a small strong smelling perennial shrub commonly found in forests as undergrowth

Family: Rutaceae

Fig.5.2 Curry Leaves

Chemical Constituent:

- **Vitamins:** Vitamin C, vitamin B, and vitamin E are all found in curry leaves. These vitamins are essential for maintaining healthy hair follicles, encouraging hair growth, and halting hair loss.
- **Antioxidants:** Because curry leaves include substances like quercetin and kaempferol, they have antioxidant qualities. These antioxidants aid in shielding the hair follicles from free radical damage and oxidative stress.

Uses:

- Straighten the roots of hair
- Promote hair growth
- Treat dandruff
- Prevents hair Graying

3.Reetha:

Synonyms: soapnut, Soapberry.

Botanical Name: *Sapindus mukorossi*

Biological Source: Reetha is a fruit of plant Deciduos tree

Family: Sapindaceae

Fig. 5.3 Reetha

Chemical Constituents:

- **Natural saponins,** especially a kind known as triterpenoids, are abundant in Reetha. When combined with water, these saponins provide a lathering effect and offer natural cleansing qualities, which makes reetha a useful natural substitute for traditional shampoos.
- **Flavonoids:** Plant substances with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, flavonoids are also present in reetha. These flavonoids may support general hair health by shielding the scalp and hair follicles from oxidative stress.

Uses:

- Promotes healthy hair
- Add shine to the hair
- Conditioning properties
- Improve scalp health

4. Aloe Vera:

Synonyms: Aloe barbadensis Mill., Aloe indica Royle, Aloe perfoliata L. var. vera

Botanical Name: Aloe barbadensis

Biological Source: It is the dried latex of the leaves of the aloe barbadensis miller plant

Family: Asphodelaceae (Liliaceae)

Fig 5.4 Aloe vera

Chemical constituent:

Vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids.

Uses:

- Strengthens hair. Aloe vera has many active ingredients and minerals that can help strengthen your hair.
- Controls greasy hair. Aloe vera has enzymes that break down fats and so strips your hair of any extra oil (sebum).
- Helps an itchy scalp.
- Protection from UV damage.

5. Flaxseeds:

Synonyms: Linseed, grain, Flaxseeds

Botanical Name: linum usitatissimum

Biological Source: Flaxseed come from the flax plant linum usitatissimum.

Family: Linaceae

Fig.5.5 Flaxseeds

Chemical Constituent:

It is a rich source of omega - 3 fatty acids especially a linolenic acid.

Uses:

- Hair growth: The B vitamins found in flaxseeds can promote the creation of red blood cells, which supply the scalp with nutrition and oxygen. They also include fiber and omega-3 fatty acids, which can increase the flexibility and strength of hair.
- Hair texture: Flaxseeds have the ability to soften, smooth, and manageably improve hair texture.
- Hair breakage: Flaxseeds can fortify hair from the ground up and stop hair breaking.

- Dry and damaged hair: Omega-3 fatty acids and vitamin E included in flaxseeds can help to nourish dry and damaged hair.
- Shine: Flaxseeds have the ability to make hair shine.

6. Lemon Juice:

Synonyms: Citrus lemon, lemon tree

Botanical Name: Citrus limon (L.) Burm.f

Biological Source: It is obtain from Citrus plant.

Family: Rutaceae.

Fig 5.6 Lemon Juice

Chemical Constituent:

These compounds include citric acid, hesperidin, diosmin, eriocitrin, and d-limonene

Uses:

- Add More shine.
- Get rid of dandruff
- Split ends
- Reduces Hair fall
- Gives Natural colour to hairs
- Detox the scalp
- Promotes the growth of hairs
- Great hair mask for dry and damage hairs

7. Hibiscus:

Synonyms: China rose, rose mallow, Hawaiian hibiscus.

Botanical Name: Hibiscus rosa-sinensis

Biological Source: The plant genus Hibiscus

Family: Malvaceae

Fig 5.7 Hibiscus Flowers

Chemical Constituent: Hibiscus flowers contain compounds like flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and amino acids, which are believed to promote hair growth, strengthen hair shafts, and improve scalp health.

Uses:

- Promoting Hair Growth and Strength:
- Stimulates Hair Follicles:
 - Hibiscus is believed to stimulate hair follicles, encouraging new hair growth and improving keratin production, which is essential for strong, healthy hair.
- Nourishes and Strengthens Hair:
 - Hibiscus is packed with essential nutrients and vitamins that nourish hair follicles, strengthening hair and reducing breakage.
 - Hibiscus can add shine and smoothness to hair, making it look healthy and vibrant.

5. Drug Profile:

Description: -

Name: Quercetin

Synonyms: 2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one

Structure:

Fig. No. 5.1: Structure Of Quercetin

AS registry No : 117-39.5 Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₀O₇

Molecular weight : 302.23g/mol

Chemical name : 2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one

Properties: Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant.

Uses: It helps to prevent hair loss

Physicochemical properties-

Melting point : 316°C

Solubility : water soluble

Storage : Room temperature

Side effects: - : Headache and upset of stomach

□ Preparation of Plant Extract:

1. Curry leaves (*Murraya koinigii*) Extract:

After letting the gathered leaves dry in the sun for two to three days, they are ground into a coarse powder with a mortar and pestle. 30g of crude powder was weighed, and the Soxhlet apparatus was used to extract the material successively using a 9:1 ratio of organic solvents, such as methanol and water. The combination underwent seven to eight consecutive rounds of heating at 60°C. On a water bath, the extract was gathered and allowed to evaporate. Finally, a phytochemical examination is performed on the isolated components.

2. Bael fruit (*Aegle Marmelos*) Extract:

Using a mortar and pestle, the gathered fruits are ground into a coarse powder after being chopped into small pieces and allowed to completely dry. Following homogenization, 30g of crude powder was weighed, and the Soxhlet apparatus was used to extract the material successively using a 9:1 ratio of organic solvents, such as methanol and water. For seven to eight consecutive cycles, the mixture was heated on a heating mantle at 60°C. On a water bath, the extract was gathered and allowed to evaporate. Finally, a phytochemical examination is performed on the isolated components.

3. Reetha (*Sapindus mukorossi*) Extract:

With just minor adjustments, the extract of *Sapindus mukorossi* was made in accordance with Chen et al. 2021. After being cleaned, 50 g of the dried *Sapindus mukorossi* (soap nut) shells were steeped in 100 ml of distilled water for the entire night. After six hours of agitation on a rotary shaker, the resulting mixture was boiled for 20

minutes at 60 degrees Celsius on a heating mantle. After allowing the extract to cool, it was centrifuged for ten minutes at 3200 rpm. After filtering, the extract was kept for the following step.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Table 6.1: List of Materials:

Sr. No	Particular	Quantity
1	Beal fruit extract	5gm
2	Curry leaves extract	5gm
3	Reetha extract	5gm
4	Aleo vera	30ml
5	Flaxseeds solution	15ml
6	Lemon juice	1ml
7	Methyl paraben	1gm
8	Hibiscus Powder	5gm
9	10% Gelatin solution	QS
10	Jasmine (perfume)	1ml

Drugs and chemicals:

Beal Fruit Extract, Curry Leaves extract, Hibiscus powder, Aloe vera, flaxseed Solution, Gelatin, Methyl Paraben, Reetha powder, Jasmine, Lemom Oil, H₂O

Glassware's and instruments:

➤ Glassware:

- Beaker
- mechanical stirrer
- weighing balance
- mortal pastle

➤ Instruments:

- Ostwald Viscometer
- Stalagmometer
- Heating mantal
- pH meter

Method of Preparations:

Steps:

A home mixer was used to dry and grind all of the herbal ingredients.

After weighing the necessary amount of components, add 15 ml of water to a separate beaker and heat for two minutes.

After that, strain the extract and combine in another beaker.

After adding the methyl paraben and citric acid, whisk in the gelatin solution and scent.

The mixture is then stored in a bottle.

7. Evaluation test: Evaluation of Prepared Herbal Shampoos:

Quality control tests, which included visual assessment and physicochemical controls like pH,

density, and viscosity, were carried out to assess the manufactured formulations. Additionally, certain tests for shampoo formulations were conducted to ensure product quality. These tests included determining the dry residue and moisture

content, surface tension, total surfactant activity, thermal and mechanical stability, and detergency.

- 1) Physical appearance visual inspection:** The formulations prepared were evaluated in terms of their clarity, foam producing ability and fluidity.
- 2) Determination of pH:** Mix 01gm of shampoo with 09ml of water and determine the pH using pH meter at 27°C.
- 3) Determine Percent of Solids Contents:** 4 grams of shampoo were added to a dry, clean evaporating dish after it had been weighed. Weighing was done on the shampoo and dish. Only the precise weight of the shampoo was determined, and the shampoo-filled evaporating dish was set on the hot plate until the liquid was gone. After drying, the weight of the shampoo alone (solids) was determined.
- 4) Rheological or Viscosity evaluations:** A Brookfield viscometer was used to measure the shampoos' viscosity. After dipping a spindle in 10 milliliters of shampoo in a beaker for approximately five minutes, a reading is taken.
- 5) Dirt dispersion :** Ten milliliters of distilled water were placed in a big test tube, and two drops of shampoo were added. After adding one drop of India ink, the test tube was sealed and shaken ten times. None, Light, Moderate, or Heavy were the estimated amounts of ink in the foam.
- 6) Surface Tension:** The surface tension of 10% w/v shampoo in distilled water was measured using stalagmometer at room temperature.
- 7) Foam Test:** The cylinder shake method was used to assess foaming capabilities. To put it briefly, a graduated cylinder was filled with 10 milliliters of the herbal shampoo solution. It was shaken ten times and covered with one hand. Following a minute of shaking, the total volume of foam content was noted. By

measuring the foam volume following a one- and four-minute shake test, foam stability was assessed.

Fig.7.1 pH of Shampoo

Fig.7.3 Physical Appearance

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

In the results we perform the different types of test and process and the values comes out from that are entered in this observation table. The values of pH, Density, and other organoleptic properties are put in this observation table.

Observation table:

Table 8.1: Observation Table:

Sr.no.	Particular	Observation
1	viscosity	Poor
2	Foaming ability	Good
3	stability	Good
4	Spreadability	Good
5	Solid content	8.5 %
6	pH	5.44 – 5.94

Table 8.2: Identification Tests:

Sr.no.	Physical properties and test	Description
1	Physical state	Liquid
2	Color	Brown
3	Odor	Sweet
4	Solubility	Water insoluble
6	Transparency	Opaque
7	Texture	Smooth

CONCLUSION:

The formulation of the herbal shampoo preparation was grounded in traditional knowledge, with a focus on creating a stable and functionally useful product. In addition to being safer than chemical conditioning agents, the shampoo formulations significantly decreased hair loss during combing and enhanced hair growth. To preserve the scalp's acidic layer, the shampoos' pH was set to 5.5. Based on traditional knowledge, the herbal shampoo formulation was created with the goal of creating a reliable and useful product.

REFERENCES

1. Kokate C.K., Purohit AP, Gokhale SB” pharmacognosy ”twenty fourth edition published by Nirali Prakashan, 2003; 343.
2. Savita S. Mali, Rekha L. Dhumal, Vijay D. Havaladar*, Snehal S. Shinde, Nilam Y. Jadhav, Bhagyashri S. Gaikwad ; A Systematic Review on *Aegle marmelos* (Bael) by Research Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry.2020;12(1).
3. Shinde PR, Tatiya AU, Surana SJ. Formulation development and evaluation of herbal antidandruff shampoo. International Journal Cosmetic Science .
4. Suyog Sunil Bhagwat, Formulation and evaluation of herbal shampoo. International Journal and Creative Research Thoughts , ISSN : 2320-2822.
5. C.T.Kulkarni , R. M. Shirke and P. B. Shinde ; Development and Evaluation of Natural Anti-Dandruff Shampoo : International Journal of Pharmaceutical science and Research ,P- ISSN : 2320-5148.
6. Herbal Shampoo: A Review", IJNRD - International Journal Of Novel Research And Development (www.IJNRD.org), ISSN:2456-4184.
7. Prachi S, Sonal D. Preparation of Herbello- an herbal anti-dandruff shampoo. Research article biological science. 2015 Apr-Jun; 5:220-221.
8. Potluri A, Asma SS, Rallapally N, Durrivel S, Harish GA. Review on herbs used in antidandruff shampoo and its evaluation parameters. Indo Am Journal Pharmacy Resistration.
9. Shinde PR, Tatiya AU, Surana SJ. Formulation development and evaluation of herbal antidandruff shampoo. International Journal Cosmetic Science.
10. Nandita Kamat, Diana Pearline, and Padama Thiagarajan Muraya koenigii (L.) A traditional Indian plant. Resarch Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Science (2015) 692.
11. Vandana Jain, Munira Momin 1, Kirti Laddha Murraya Koenigii : An Updated Review, International Journal Of Ayurvedic And Herbal Medicine 2:4 (2012).
12. Kancharla.Kameswararao*, B.Lakshmi prasanna, M.Aparnadevi,

- G.Nagadevi, S.Rajeswari.: formulation and evaluation of polyherbal shampoo . *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research* ISSN 2349-7203.
13. Miss Waghmode Monika Vasant, Dr. Hingane L. D. "Formulation and evaluation of herbal shampoo", *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)* volume 10, issue 4 June 2022.
 14. Tanya Malpani, Manali Jeithliya, Nanadini Pal and Payal Puri "Formulation and evaluation of Pomegranate based herbal shampoo", *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 2020.
 15. Ashwini VJ, Dipak M, Daundekar A, Bhujbal N, Kshirsagar S. Hebal hair cosmetics-An Overview. *World J of Pharm Sci.* 2018; 6(9):144-152.
 16. Virendra Tiwari, Rashmi Singh, AK Pandey. *Aegle marmelos: Pharmacological, Medicinal importance and Conservation in India.* *Journal of Experimental Zoology.* 2018;21(1):11-18.
 17. Ishita Kumari, Ishita Sarkar, Ishita Sanyanishi, Sayak Das and Rajat Das " Formulation and evaluation of herbal shampoo using neem, amla and reetha extract", *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry.* Vol.11, issue 4 (2022)
 18. .Beena Kumari "Taxonomy and ethnobotany of *Murraya koenigii* (L.) Spreng: An exotic shrub in Rohilkhand region of Uttar Pradesh", *Journal of medicinal plants studies*, 2018.
 19. Mr. Abhijit V. Tambe, Mr. Rohit H. Phapale, Mr. Prathamesh S. Shingote, Prof. Sagar E. Tambe "Formulation and evaluation of herbal shampoo from fermented rice water and its antifungal activity", *International Journal of Advance Research in Science Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)* volume 2, issue 1, June 2022.
 20. .Mrs. K. Sravanthi, N. Kavitha, K. Sowmya, S. Naazneen, U. Vaishanvi, CH. Anil A review on "Formulation and evaluation of herbal anti dandruff shampoo", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications*, volume 6, issue 3 May- June 2021 pp:1300-1311.
 21. Priya D. Gaikwad, Kamini V. Mulay, Madhavee D. Borrade "Formulation and Evaluation of herbal shampoo", *International Journal of science and Research (IJSR)*
 22. Khaloud AL Badi, Shah A. Khan "Formulation, evaluation and comparison of herbal shampoo with the commercial shampoos", *Beni- Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, volume 3, issue 4, December 23014, page no. 301-305
 23. Gaurav Lodha "formulation and evaluation of polyherbal shampoo to promote hair growth and provide Antidandruff Action", *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 2019;9 (4-A): 296-300.

HOW TO CITE: Vaishali Bhavale*, Aarti Dangode, Priya Jaware, Dr. Santosh Payghan, *Formulation and Evolution of Polyherbal Shampoo*, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 9336-9348 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15229505>

